

Evaluating carbon footprints of weed management in greengram (*Vigna radiata*. L)

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted during summer season of 2022 at Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai to evaluate the carbon footprints. Experiment was carried out in Randomized block design with three replication. The treatments namely T₁- Sulfentrazone 0.20 kg ha⁻¹ e+ as PPI, T₂- Sulfentrazone 0.30 kg ha⁻¹ e+ as PPI, T₃- Sulfentrazone 0.40 kg ha⁻¹ e+ as PPI, T₄-Sulfentrazone 0.20 kg ha⁻¹ e+ as PEA, T₅-Sulfentrazone 0.30 kg ha⁻¹ e+ as PEA, T₆- Sulfentrazone 0.40 kg ha⁻¹ e+ as PEA, T₇- Sulfentrazone 0.20 kg ha⁻¹ e- as PPI, T₈- Sulfentrazone 0.30 kg ha⁻¹ e- as PPI, T₉-Sulfentrazone 0.40 kg ha⁻¹ e- as PPI, T₁₀- Sulfentrazone 0.20 kg ha⁻¹ e- as PEA, T₁₁- Sulfentrazone 0.30 kg ha⁻¹ e- as PEA, T₁₂- Sulfentrazone 0.40 kg ha⁻¹ e- as PEA and T₁₃- Absolute control. Sulfentrazone 0.30 kg ha⁻¹ e+ as PPI registered low toxicity among encapsulated sulfentrazone formulation.

Introduction

Weeds are an important biotic factor in the yield reduction of crops and they cause more economic losses than other abiotic and biotic factors. However, there is a significant difference in economic losses by weeds between various crops, locations, and soil types (Gharde *et al.*, 2018). The management of weeds infestation in different pulse crop has the potential to increase the sustaining production and productivity (Strydhorst *et al.*, 2008). In India, Greengram is the third highly prized pulse crop, followed by chickpea and pigeonpea. It is cultivated under an area of about 5.55 M ha, with a production of 3.16 M ha and the productivity of 570 kg ha⁻¹ (Indiastat, 2022). Weeds mainly compete with crops for nutrients, space, and water and therefore, it can reduce the yield up to 45 to 60%. In this context, weed eradication at suitable time with adequate methodology is very important to attain a crop yield. However, labour scarcity and continuous rainfall make manual weeding impracticable. Therefore, chemical weeding is the only viable option enabling the nano-science with herbicides make better one.

Material and methods

Field trial was carried out in Agricultural college and research institute, Madurai which is located in the southern zone of Tamil Nadu during Rabi 2022 and greengram variety of VBN 4 was used as a test crop. Design executed was Randomized Block Design (RBD) and it was replicated thrice. Treatment details are furnished in Table 1

C budget is important for quantifying changes in the C cycle by anthropogenic activities. Carbon budgeting of various weed management treatments need to be computed to find out the most efficient weed control treatment with a high carbon sustainability index. As suggested by Lal *et al.*, (2019) the inputs and outputs were multiplied by the carbon emission coefficients shown in **Table 2**. to calculate the carbon equivalents as given below

$$\text{Carbon output (kg CE ha}^{-1}\text{)} = \text{Total biomass (Grain yield+ by-product yield)* 0.44}$$

$$\text{Carbon efficiency} = \frac{\text{Total Carbon output}}{\text{Total carbon input}}$$

$$\text{Carbon sustainability index} = \frac{\text{Total carbon output}-\text{Total carbon input}}{\text{Total carbon input}}$$

$$\text{Carbon footprints} = \frac{\text{Total Carbon emission or input}}{\text{The total yield of crop}}$$

Table 1 Treatment details of experiment

T.No	Treatments
T ₁	Sulfentrazone 0.3kg ha ⁻¹ e+ as pre-plant incorporation (PPI)
T ₂	Sulfentrazone 0.3kg ha ⁻¹ e- as pre-plant incorporation (PPI)
T ₃	Sulfentrazone 0.3kg ha ⁻¹ e+ as pre-emergence application (PEA)
T ₄	Sulfentrazone 0.3 kg ha ⁻¹ e- as pre-emergence application(PEA)
T ₅	Pendimethalin 30EC+Imazethapyr 2EC @0.75 Kg a.i.ha ⁻¹ as PEA <i>fb</i> Hand wedding on 20 DAS
T ₆	Pendemethalin @ 1kga.i. ha ⁻¹ as PEA <i>fb</i> HW on 20 DAS
T ₇	Handweeding15and30DAS
T ₈	Weed free check
T ₉	No weeding (weedy check)

Table.2

Inputs	Units	Carbon Emission Coefficient
Seeds	Kg	0.32
Human labor	Man-day	0.23
Machinery	H	0.89
Diesel	L	0.94
Water application	m ³	0.17
Nitrogen	kg	1.3
Phosphorus	kg	0.2
Potassium	kg	0.15
Insecticides	kg. a.i	5.1
Herbicide	kg .a.i	6.3
Straw	kg	0.44

Result and discussion

Carbon budgeting

The inputs and outputs were multiplied by the carbon emission coefficients to calculate the carbon equivalents and are given in the Table.51 and 52. The total value of the carbon inputs and outputs were calculated

Total carbon input

The total carbon input is a decimal parameter, that derived from the carbon emission coefficients to indicating the amount of carbon included in each treatments .Among, the weed management practices tried, an carbon input of 192.68 kg CE ha⁻¹ was obtained under weed free check (T₈) followed by application of pendimethalin 30 EC + imazethapyr 2EC @ 0.75 kg a.i.ha⁻¹ as PEA *fb* hand wedding on 20 DAS (T₅) with 189.18 kg CE ha⁻¹. Weedy check (T₉) recorded minimum total carbon input of 168.18 kg CE ha⁻¹.

Carbon output by grains

Carbon output by grains was observed maximum with weed free check (T₈), which gives the output of 444.48 CE ha⁻¹ in summer. Following this, application of encapsulated sulfentrazone @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre-plant incorporation (T₁) yielded 420.80 CE ha⁻¹. The minimum carbon output was registered under weedy check (T₉) with 168.18 CE ha⁻¹.

Carbon output by straw

The carbon output by straw followed the same trend as that of output recorded by grains. Carbon output by straw was observed maximum under weed free check (T₈) with 1636.36 in summer was followed by application of encapsulated sulfentrazone applied @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre- plant incorporation (T₁) and registered 1573.88 CE ha⁻¹. Whereas it was minimum under weedy check (T₉) with the output of 837.32 kg CE ha⁻¹ respectively of summer

Total carbon output

The accounting on the total carbon output showed that the maximum total carbon output was observed with weed free check (T₈) in both the seasons respectively of 2080.84 kg CE ha⁻¹. Application of encapsulated sulfentrazone applied @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre-plant incorporation (T₁) closely followed the weed free check (T₈) and gave the output of 1994.68 kg CE ha⁻¹. Minimum was under weedy check (T₉) and yielded with the output of 939.72 kg CE ha⁻¹.

Carbon efficiency

Application of encapsulated sulfentrazone @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre-plant incorporation (T₁) recorded higher carbon efficiency of 11.42 in summer followed by encapsulated sulfentrazone applied @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre-emergence (T₃) with 11.29. Carbon efficiency was minimum with weedy check (T₉) and recorded with 5.59 during summer .

Carbon sustainability index

Carbon sustainability index measure carbon reduction in terms of absolute carbon emission. High value denotes high carbon reduction in terms of carbon emission. Application of encapsulated sulfentrazone @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre-plant incorporation (T₁) recorded higher carbon sustainability index of 10.42 in summer followed by encapsulated sulfentrazone applied @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre-emergence (T₃) with carbon sustainability index of 10.29. Whereas, carbon sustainability index was minimum with weedy check (T₉) and recorded 4.59 in summer **Carbon footprint**

A carbon footprint is the total amount of greenhouse gases (including carbon dioxide and methane) that are generated by each treatments. High carbon footprints implies higher release of carbon emissions. Weedy check (T₉) recorded higher carbon footprint of about

0.53 and 0.51 kg CE kg⁻¹ yield in summer. It was followed by application of pendemethalin @ 1 kg a.i. ha⁻¹ as PEA *fb* HW on 20 DAS (T₆) with carbon foot print yield of 0.23 kg CE kg⁻¹. Whereas carbon footprint was recorded minimum under encapsulated sulfentrazone applied @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre- plant incorporation (T₁) which accounted 0.13 kg CE kg⁻¹ yield.

Higher carbon output was recorded in encapsulated sulfentrazone applied @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre-plant incorporation (1994 kg CE ha⁻¹) and pre- emergence (2059 kg CE ha⁻¹) as the highest yield was observed in this treatments because of the higher efficacy in the weed control (**Fig 1**). The difference in carbon inputs among various treatments was mainly attributed to the difference in the herbicide doses and active ingredients in the herbicides. The minimum carbon outputs were observed in the weedy check because of the uncontrolled weed growth, leading to the lowest yield. Consequently, the carbon efficiency and carbon sustainability index were also observed to be maximum in encapsulated sulfentrazone applied @ 0.3 kg ha⁻¹ as pre-plant incorporation and pre- emergence, which also yielded the lowest carbon footprint. The higher output per unit of input ensured a higher carbon sustainability index (CSI) and lower carbon footprints. Similar results are also observed by Maheswarappa *et al.*, (2011) and Wang *et al.*, (2015).

References

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Effect of weed management treatments on carbon consumption, carbon output and carbon footprints in greengram crop during summer 2023

T.No	Treatments	Total C input (kg CE ha ⁻¹)	Carbon output by grains (kg CE ha ⁻¹)	Carbon output by straw (kg CE ha ⁻¹)	Total carbon output (kg CE ha ⁻¹)	Carbon Efficiency	Carbon sustainability index (CSI)	Carbon footprint (kg CE kg ⁻¹ yield)
T ₁	Sulfentrazone 0.3 kg ha ⁻¹ e+ as pre- plant incorporation (PPI)	174.59	420.80	1573.88	1994.68	11.42	10.42	0.13
T ₂	Sulfentrazone 0.3 kg ha ⁻¹ e- as pre- plant incorporation (PPI)	174.59	353.60	1408.00	1761.60	10.09	9.09	0.16
T ₃	Sulfentrazone 0.3 kg ha ⁻¹ e+ as pre- emergence application (PEA)	174.59	413.76	1556.72	1970.48	11.29	10.29	0.14
T ₄	Sulfentrazone 0.3 kg ha ⁻¹ e- as pre- emergence application (PEA)	174.59	351.68	1403.60	1755.28	10.05	9.05	0.16
T ₅	Pendimethalin 30 EC + Imazethapyr 2EC @ 0.75 Kg a.i.ha ⁻¹ as PEA fb Hand wedding on 20 DAS	189.18	294.40	1263.24	1557.64	8.23	7.23	0.21
T ₆	Pendemethalin @ 1 kg a.i. ha ⁻¹ as PEA fb HW on 20 DAS	187.87	259.20	1172.60	1431.80	7.62	6.62	0.23
T ₇	Hand weeding 15 and 30 DAS	179.68	255.36	1093.40	1348.76	7.51	6.51	0.23
T ₈	Weed free check	192.68	444.48	1636.36	2080.84	10.80	9.80	0.14
T ₉	No weeding (weedy check)	168.18	102.4	837.32	939.72	5.59	4.59	0.53

Information not statistically analysed

Influence of different weed management treatments on carbon budgeting of greengram during summer 2023